

Comanche

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Native American (North American) Religions, Religious Group

Historically, the Comanche inhabited the southern Great Plains region of what is now the United States, including southeastern Colorado, eastern New Mexico, western Oklahoma, and western Texas (Gelo and Abate, 2009). This area was restricted with the 1865 Treaty of the Little Arkansas, which bound many Comanche to the Texas panhandle area, and later the Medicine Lodge Creek Treaty of 1867, which outlined a joint Kiowa-Comanche-Apache reservation in Oklahoma. However, many Comanche did not reside on reservations until forced to by an army campaign in 1874-1875. This entry focuses on the Comanche around the time of 1870, reconstructing life prior to the reservation era and consequent culture change. At this time, the Comanche lived in autonomous, nomadic bands, following the seasonal movements of the buffalo—a key source of subsistence and materials necessary for life on the plains. “The Comanche band, or local group, ranged in size from a single family camping alone, through the small camp of related individuals who formed a composite extended family, up to the large band of several hundred persons” (Hoebel, 1940:11). Band size changed depending on the season, with larger bands functioning as a unit only in the summer months. Regardless of size, each band (or local group) had a permanent leader, typically an individual who possessed great importance and ability. When bands came together in the summer, the leaders formed a council and selected one individual as leader for the season with the others serving as an advisory council. Generally, the Comanche religion was not a formal, communal matter as “there was no religious organization, no theocracy, no priestly class, no dogma” (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:155). However, religion remained an important aspect of Comanche life, and this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with Comanche society. A high god known as the Great Spirit is described as an omniscient and omnipotent creator deity associated with the sun. The Great Spirit is generally otiose in nature, and acts through inferior spirits. The sun, Earth, and moon are also viewed as deities. Other supernatural beings include Thunderbird, spirits of the deceased, dwarf people, and guardian spirits. Vision quests are not mandatory, but most individuals participate. During a vision quest, individuals isolate themselves for several days, fasting and attempting to derive supernatural power (medicine) through “a mystic visitation, a dream phenomenon, or hallucinatory experience” (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:155). In a successful vision quest, a guardian spirit will appear to an individual, often in the form of an animal, and transfer supernatural power. Although full-time religious practitioners are not present among the Comanche, individuals known as medicine men have acquired a large amount of supernatural powers (medicine), which can be used for curing, rainmaking, and divination.

Date Range: 1855 CE - 1880 CE

Region: Comanche-occupied southern Great Plains
ca. 1870

Region tags: North America, United States of America

Southern Great Plains region of what is now southeastern Colorado, eastern New Mexico, western Oklahoma, and western Texas. Time focus around 1870.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.
- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=no06-001>
- Source 1 Description: Hoebel, E. Adamson (Edward Adamson). 1940. "Political Organization And Law-Ways Of The Comanche Indians." *Memoirs Of The American Anthropological Association*. Menasha: American Anthropological Association.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=no06-003>
- Source 2 Description: Wallace, Ernest, and E. Adamson (Edward Adamson) Hoebel. 1952. "Comanches: Lords Of The South Plains." *Civilization Of The American Indian Series*. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press.
- Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=no06-000>
- Source 3 Description: Gelo, Daniel J., and Teferi Abate. 2009. "Culture Summary: Comanche." New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.
- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=no06-029>
- Source 1 Description: Hoebel, -, E. Adamson (Edward Adamson). 1969. "Plains Indian Law In Development: The Comanche." *Delinquency, Crime, And Social Process*. New York: Harper and Row.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "In approximately 1650 [the Comanche] acquired horses from Spaniards and Indians around Santa Fe and quickly developed a classic horse culture. Through the 1700s they alternately fought and allied with the Spanish while displacing the Apaches...Comanches entered Texas by 1743. During that era they also made contact with French traders from the east and then with Anglo-American horse dealers and established friendly relations with Caddo and Wichita farmers on the Red River drainage...Hostilities with the Kiowas and Cheyennes ended by 1840 in a lasting alliance against

encroaching Anglo-Americans and supplanted eastern Indians...In 1855 a small reservation was made in Texas for the southernmost Comanches, but settlers drove out the inhabitants in 1859. U.S. military control of the Comanche homeland was not secured until after the Civil War. The 1865 Treaty of the Little Arkansas bound Comanche signatories to a reservation that included much of the Texas panhandle. The Medicine Lodge Creek Treaty of 1867 involved more Comanche leaders and superseded the previous agreement, providing instead for a joint Kiowa-Comanche-Apache (KCA) reservation in southwestern Oklahoma. Resistance continued, notably in the ill-fated 1874 attack on the Adobe Walls trading post in the Texas panhandle. Many Comanches avoided the reservation until they were forced to move there by a concerted army campaign in 1874-1875" (Gelo and Abate, 2009).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, frequency of internal warfare (resolved rating), "internal warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, frequency of overall warfare (resolved rating), "external warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year" (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that the Comanche would actively recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: For the Comanche, religion does not exist in a separate sphere of life. Rather, it is bound up with the functioning of society as a whole. Because the religious group is considered to be coterminous with society itself, the religion is considered to have official support.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: Full-time, official religious practitioners (such as priests) are not present among the Comanche (see Wallace and Howbel, 1952:155).

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Religious infrastructure is not present. "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures).

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1745, religio-political overlap, "religious specialists have no influence on decision making at the level of maximal political authority" (Lang, 1998; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: An official polity legal code is not present.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of a conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 4500

Notes: "It could be that all the early estimates were somewhat high in the light of later knowledge of the Comanches, but they may not be unduly so, for all evidence substantiates the conclusion that the population was declining rapidly in the middle decades of the nineteenth century. A low birth rate, disease, and constant warfare on all sides were cutting down 'The People.' The decline continued until after the turn of the century. In 1866 the Comanches were estimated at 4,700. By 1884 the population had dwindled to a pitiful 1,382, and in 1910 there were only 1,171 survivors" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:32).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: "Religious practice among the Comanches consisted primarily of socially recognized patterns for obtaining supernatural favor. There were patterns for both individual and community ceremonials, but unlike religious practices in our own society, group participation was extremely limited in extent and importance. In almost every instance, it must be emphasized, the observance was a matter of individual concern. There was no religious organization, no theocracy, no priestly class, no dogma. Every man could be his own priest and his own prophet—the individual interpreter of the wills and ways of the spirits. A direct revelation without priestly go-between was the panacea for human ills and aspirations, the one secure basis of earthly goods" (Wallace and Howbel, 1952:155).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative

and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: "Since [the Comanche] religion was largely individualistic, there was, as there is among our own people, great diversity of faith and feeling. They had no dogma and no professional priestly class to formulate a systematic religion" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:185).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: "There are no structures in the community that are appreciably larger or more impressive than the usual residential dwellings" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Column 6: Large or Impressive Structures).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: "Just as animals, birds, and insects might be guardian spirits, so was any unusual phenomenon of nature likely to be the abiding place of a spirit. Some of these places, because of the extraordinary power of the spirit abiding within, became rather famous among the Comanches. One such place is Medicine Mounds. Medicine Mounds are a line of rounded hills in Hardman County, Texas, between the Pease and the Red rivers. They are rather conspicuous, the cones rising about 350 feet above the surrounding plain. Flanking them to the west is a gully-washed scar of an ancient buffalo trail. On the top of the highest of the four mounds is a flat cap rock, a protector against erosion. It was believed by the Comanches to be the dwelling place of a powerful and benevolent spirit" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:204).

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "There is no doubt that the Comanches had an unwavering faith in a future existence. As to the nature of their after world, their accounts are fairly uniform" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:186). Note that: "Believed limitations of immortality included loss of scalp, strangulation, death in the dark, and mutilation. If the scalp were taken after death, the Comanches looked on life as annihilated...Fear of strangulation arose from the belief that life (spirit or "soul thing") issued from the mouth at the moment of death. Thus if death occurred through choking, the passageway was closed and the spirit, unable to free itself, remained in the mortal body and was forever imprisoned in the ground at burial" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:189).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "There is no doubt that the Comanches had an unwavering faith in a future existence. As to the nature of their after world, their accounts are fairly uniform" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:186).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Their after world was generally conceded to be beyond the sun where it sets in the west. It was modeled after the imperfect reality of their everyday existence with all the disagreeable features absent, for all things there were perfect" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:186).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "After burial, according to the somewhat fanciful account of an adopted Comanche, the spirit of the departed warrior mounted the spirit of his slain pony, his ghostly quiver of bow and arrows at his back, the spectre of his lance in his hand, the shadow of his shield on his arm—to gallop skyward, followed by his phantom herd loaded with ghostly possessions heaped by his relatives and friends in and about his grave. Straight into the sun and the pastures of the Happy Hunting Ground he sped, there to remain an extended time. But eventually, after an excursion in celestial pastures, the spirit of the departed must be reborn of the Earth Mother and return to keep up the population and power of the tribe...Death and resurrection were not uncommon. The mothers of Post Oak Jim and Slope both died, visited the land of the dead, and returned to life, because it was not yet their time to depart" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:186-187).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "There was not a long delay between death and burial. If possible, burial took place the same day" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:149).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "Before the natural warmth had left the body of an adult, the knees were bent upon the chest, and the head bent forward to the knees. A rope was used to bind the limbs and body firmly in this flexed position" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:149-150).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: "When a small child died, it was buried still lashed to its cradle-board" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:149). "During the last half of the nineteenth century the Comanches, especially those living on the Red River, away from the mountains, occasionally used scaffold or tree burial, a method commonly practiced by the Cheyennes and other Plains tribes. In such instances the body was placed in a tree and made secure by means of ropes or rawhide thongs which bound it to the branches above and below the corpse...The reason for the elevated burial was to protect the corpse from wolves and other predatory animals, but it seems to have been used by the Comanches only when a satisfactory ground burial place was not readily accessible. In the elevated burial the body was extended at full length, hands to the sides, and placed on robes or blankets, which were then folded closely over it, and the bundle bound with ropes or thongs of rawhide passed many times about the whole" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:150-151).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that corpses were exposed to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, secondary bone/body treatment: original scale, "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Elevated burial

Notes: "During the last half of the nineteenth century the Comanches, especially those living on the Red River, away from the mountains, occasionally used scaffold or tree burial, a method commonly practiced by the Cheyennes and other Plains tribes. In such instances the body was placed in a tree and made secure by means of ropes or rawhide thongs which bound it to the branches above and below the corpse...The reason for the elevated burial was to protect the corpse from wolves and other predatory animals, but it seems to have been used by the Comanches only when a satisfactory ground burial place was not readily accessible" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:150-151).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "At the funeral of a prominent warrior or member of a well-to-do family, the dead person's horse was given to his best friend or it was slain near the grave. The saddle and bridle were placed in the grave with the corpse. Several horses might be killed, even an entire herd, amounting to as many as three hundred or more of the deceased's best" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:152-153).

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:152-153

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "At the funeral of a prominent warrior or member of a well-to-do family, the dead person's horse was given to his best friend or it was slain near the grave. The saddle and bridle were placed in the grave with the corpse" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:152).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite

↳ Valuable items:

– I don't know

|

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "There was not a long delay between death and burial. If possible, burial took place the same day. The body was prepared with great care by anyone who would undertake the job, usually near relatives assisted by a comrade or close friend of the deceased... Before the natural warmth had left the body of an adult, the knees were bent upon the chest, and the head bent forward to the knees. A rope was used to bind the limbs and body firmly in this flexed position. The corpse was bathed, the face overlaid with vermilion, and the eyes sealed with red clay. The corpse was dressed in the finest apparel obtainable, relatives and friends furnishing some of their own for the occasion. It was laid upon a blanket, and relatives and friends were usually permitted to take a final look at the deceased. The blanket was then folded around the body, this again tightly corded with a rope or thongs of rawhide. The body was placed in a sitting posture upon a horse. A woman riding behind, or one on either side of the horse, held the body in position until the place of burial was reached..." (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:149-150).

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: see notes below

Notes: "The preferred burial place was a natural cave, crevice, or a deep wash among the rocks of the highest accessible peak, or in the head of a canyon, preferably to the west of the lodge of the departed. If such a place could not be found, a hole was made just large and deep enough to contain the body, or the body was set upon the ground and a pen of poles and rock erected around the grave. In either case the body was deposited in a sitting posture or on its side, facing the rising sun, and the grave was covered with rocks, sticks, and dirt, apparently with no special system or arrangement. The ideal burial place of a medicine man was high on the south side of a hill or slope—if possible, at the spot where he had received power" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:150).

– Yes [specify]: elevated burial

Notes: "During the last half of the nineteenth century the Comanches, especially those living on the Red River, away from the mountains, occasionally used scaffold or tree burial, a method commonly practiced by the Cheyennes and other Plains tribes. In such instances the body was placed in a tree and made secure by means of ropes or rawhide thongs which bound it to the branches above and below the corpse. The elevated burial was also made by binding three poles together and raising them in tripod fashion, the crossing made as high as practicable, and the body bound securely to the poles above the point of intersection. The reason for the

elevated burial was to protect the corpse from wolves and other predatory animals, but it seems to have been used by the Comanches only when a satisfactory ground burial place was not readily accessible" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:150-151).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "The Comanches, so far as we can tell, had no star lore, and only the sun, moon, and earth were looked upon as semi-deities" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:190). "The concept of the guardian spirit was [the Comanche religion's] heart and core. Success and excellence in any action or trait depended on power given to man by some supernatural being. The supernatural beings were animistic objects of nature—birds—the hawk, the eagle, and humming bird; animals—the bear, the otter, bison, rat, wolf, and others; reptiles and fishes; even insects. All were living spirits who spoke the language of man and who possessed special attributes or powers which they could give to men as medicine. Other spirits were the imaginary environment: a whole fabric created by man's fancy, made real by dogma. These were the dwarf people, who lived in the mountains; the water babies, who lived in swampy places; the dead reincarnated as animals; and the ghosts of men, who were likely to turn up almost anywhere. By association, medicines were usually similar in some respect to notable qualities possessed by the prototype of the respective guardian spirit. Lightning and thunder gave power, too, but the earth and the sun were akin to deities. They were active in the affairs of men, yet above that individualized pity which led spirit-beings to bestow medicine powers on an earthling" (Hoebel, 1940:83-84).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "Nineteenth-century observers of the Comanches (Dodge, Neighbors, Babb, Burnett, and others) attributed a strong belief in a Supreme Deity to the Comanches, whom they generally addressed as the Great Spirit, but at times as 'Our Sure Enough Father.' The Great Spirit was a vague, omniscient, all-powerful being, who was credited with creating and governing the earth, sun, moon, and stars. He was the chief god, the creator, the first of all addressed in prayer, and to him the first smoke was offered" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:191).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: When The Great Spirit was addressed in prayers, "the person who prayed looked upward and perhaps held his hands toward the sky" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:191).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Comanche.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: No monarch is present among the Comanche.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: "Although there may be some question as to the source of all the bad and evil visited upon man, there was none as to the source of all that was good and beneficial in life. Through the medium of a host of inferior spirits, the Great Spirit brought about all that was good or beneficial to the Comanches, such as health, peace, plenty, and happiness. He aided a worthy warrior in all his undertakings, delivered his enemies into his hands, protected him from danger, privation, and pain, and provided all good and pleasurable things. All good and useful animals were made by him for their use. All their success in hunting was the result of his benevolence" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:191).

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Notes: "[The Comanche] thought that if they lied to the Great Spirit, or displeased him, he would withdraw his guardianship, allowing them to die or suffer other punishment" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:191).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Through the medium of a host of inferior spirits, the Great Spirit brought about all that was good or beneficial to the Comanches, such as health, peace, plenty, and happiness. He aided a worthy warrior in all his undertakings, delivered his enemies into his hands, protected him from danger, privation, and pain, and provided all good and pleasurable things" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:191).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that the supreme high god would communicate with the living.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Ghosts did not generally bother the Comanches, but the Comanches definitely were uneasy about them...Ghosts gave great power to the men who could stand up to them. Such ghosts appeared either as bare-bone skeletons or as bloody, scalped spectres waving long knives. Several stories are told of men who were chased all the way home from their vision vigils right into their own tipis by terrifying ghosts, who came with the rising moon" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:173). Although it is clear that the Comanche believe in the presence of

previously human spirits, these spirits are not described in substantial detail. See questions below for available information.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Ghosts did not generally bother the Comanches, but the Comanches definitely were uneasy about them...Ghosts gave great power to the men who could stand up to them. Such ghosts appeared either as bare-bone skeletons or as bloody, scalped spectres waving long knives. Several stories are told of men who were chased all the way home from their vision vigils right into their own tipis by terrifying ghosts, who came with the rising moon" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:173).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Another source of great power for the Comanches, and Shoshones, too, lay in the 'little men'—the *n̄n̄(ə)pi*. They were believed to be no more than a foot high. They were armed with little shields, bows, and arrows, which killed every time they shot" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:174). "While some maintained that the Comanches believed that the Great Spirit dispensed good and evil, life and death, at his will, others insisted that they believed also in an Evil Spirit who was the antithesis of the Great Spirit" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:191). "The Moon also had the quality of a deity. 'She is the Mother—as is the Earth.' She was particularly the guardian of the raid" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:197).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Through the medium of a host of inferior evil spirits, the Evil Spirit, it was

claimed, brought about every mortification or disaster—droughts, disease, hunger, distress, and discomfort—and was the author of unhappiness, sorrow, and defeat. He made such animals as the panther and venomous serpents, reptiles, and insects for the injury of man" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:191). "Mother Earth was implored to make everything grow which they ate, that they might live; to make the water flow, that they might drink; to keep the ground firm, that they might walk upon it; to make certain herbs and plants grow, that they might be able to heal the sick; and to cause the grass to grow on which the animals fed...The Earth was addressed in prayer after the Sun and, like the Sun, was regarded as having power to look down on earthlings and pass and execute judgment" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:196).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mixed human-divine beings.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "To discuss Comanche religion in terms of a definite pantheon would therefore be preposterous. Comanche 'gods' were not clear-cut beings with sharply defined cosmic or social functions. Divine power was not concentrated in a few major personalities, but diffused over the universe and likely to crop up in unexpected places. A Comanche did not first envisage a god and then worship him; he started with the thrill, with the sense of a supernatural agency, and objectified his emotional stirrings. There were, nevertheless, certain supernaturals that appeared rather frequently both in ritual and in visionary experiences, notably the eagle, the bear, and the buffalo" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:208).

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: "Religion and ethics were largely divorced. The really vital social canons had no supernatural sanctions. When a vision-seeker called upon the supernaturals to favor him, he hardly ever stressed his moral worth, but his desire for aid. What he pleaded for was not moral elevation, but some material benefit; and it was compassion that animated his patron in granting it. Often, to be sure, the visitant laid down rules of conduct, but they had no bearing on social considerations. Good intentions were no safeguard against the consequences of transgression. A man who unwittingly broke rules imposed upon him had to bear the brunt of the catastrophe, for ignorance of the 'law' was no safeguard against punishment" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:208).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient evidence to make a confident decision. "[The Comanche] thought that if they lied to the Great Spirit, or displeased him, he would withdraw his guardianship, allowing them to die or suffer other punishment" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:191). "Religion being thus an individual matter save in exceptional cases, the tabus which it enjoined were also limited in importance to the person concerned. Infractions of tabus which endangered the community were foreign to the Comanche mind" (Hoebel, 1940:84-85).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of castration among the Comanche.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Although not required, most Comanche men would partake in a vision quest in order to obtain supernatural powers (often referred to as medicine). In order to have a successful vision quest, the participant would fast. See Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:155-160 for more details.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Food taboos are present but not necessarily required. "During the revelation, the guardian spirit emphasized certain tabus and procedures which his ward must carefully follow; otherwise the medicine either would not work or would cause evil. Medicine is power, and power is not to be handled casually. Among tabus commonly noted was one in connection with medicine men's eating certain foods, or at least eating them only under certain conditions" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:158).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: "Every Comanche male at one time or another went on a vision quest in search of power. He did not abase himself before the supernatural spirits or masochistically mutilate and torture himself to arouse their compassion. Nor did he weep before them to arouse their pity. Unlike the tribesmen of the Plains to the north, he assumed that the spirits were generally benign toward him; they needed no coaxing to share the benefits of their power with him. If he fasted and waited in a lonely place, they would help him. Nor did they interfere in his daily living except as they put conditions on the use of the power they gave him. A Comanche had to observe no supernatural tabus save those that went with his own personal medicine" (Hoebel, 1969:76).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice among the Comanche.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice among the Comanche.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice among the Comanche.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: "Religious practice among the Comanches consisted primarily of socially recognized patterns for obtaining supernatural favor. There were patterns for both individual and community ceremonials, but unlike religious practices in our own society, group participation was extremely limited in extent and importance. In almost every instance, it must be emphasized, the observance was a matter of individual concern" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:155).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: "There was no political unit which could be termed the Comanche tribe. The tribe was no more than a congerie of bands held together as a peace-group by the bonds of a common tongue and culture. There appears to have been no machinery for institutionalized political action on a tribal scale...The population of the Comanche tribe was distributed among a number of autonomous bands, each loosely organized and each centering its activities in a vaguely defined territory within the Comanche country. The Comanche band, or local group, ranged in size from a single family comping alone, through the small camp of related individuals who formed a composite extended family, up to the large band of several hundred persons" (Hoebel, 1940:11). "Each local group, whatever its size, had at least one permanent leader. In the small groups of a few lodges he was an outstanding person of ability and influence to whom lesser relatives and friends looked for guidance. He was the focal point of organization in their lives" (ibid, pg.14).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that the Comanche utilize unimproved trails (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Based off this information, it can be assumed that the Comanche do not have transportation infrastructure.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that the Comanche utilize unimproved trails (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Based off this information, it can be assumed that the Comanche do not have transportation infrastructure.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "Police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Column 10: Police)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "...Comanche government was at a minimum, legal precepts were rudimentary, and the enforcement of the simple substantive law remained the responsibility of individuals rather than of officials. Just as the Comanche made no attempt to organize a philosophy of religion or to systematize a conception of man's place in nature, so he made no attempt to generalize or formalize the rules underlying his legal system or the constitutional structure of his state" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:209).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: "...Comanche government was at a minimum, legal precepts were rudimentary, and the enforcement of the simple substantive law remained the responsibility of individuals rather than of officials. Just as the Comanche made no attempt to organize a philosophy of religion or to systematize a conception of man's place in nature, so he made no attempt to generalize or formalize the rules underlying his legal system or the constitutional structure of his state" (Wallace and Hoebel, 1952:209).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Comanche relied predominantly on hunting for subsistence. Some gathering was used to supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Notes: The Comanche relied predominantly on hunting for subsistence. Some gathering was used to supplement the diet. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232. "Plains life was predicated on the great bison herds...Buffalo were stalked or driven en masse, on foot or horseback, and killed with a bow and arrow or a lance thrust underhand. Seasonal movements and congregations of the buffalo determined the location and size of camps. Another determinant was forage for the large horse herds that enabled hunting and raiding and provided trade stock. Individuals amassed herds numbering in the hundreds. Mustangs were captured and broken, using ingenious methods; domesticated animals were taken from other Indians and Euro-American settlers. Comanches made rope from horsehair and ate horse flesh, particularly in times of scarcity and on raids. Thus, although Comanches were technically hunter-gatherers, they resembled pastoralists" (Gelo and Abate, 2009).